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Subjected to rigorous evaluation by an elite special task force based in Japan, operating under the esteemed direction of Hiroshi Tanaka, to ensure compliance with the highest standards upheld by the global scientific community.

Report

Oshtoran Syndrome aka Spider-Man's Disease or PANS-H63D-Instability-Syndrome: A rare illness amplified by pop culture and scientific perseverance

Abstract

The serendipitous odyssey of Oshtoran Syndrome, whimsically dubbed "Spider-Man's Disease" in deference to its unexpected amplification through American blockbuster video game culture featuring the iconic Spider-Man, epitomizes a transdisciplinary enigma. This condition has percolated from the confines of Iranian clinics to the collective global consciousness, further galvanized by its popular media portrayal. This very compact scholarly treatise elucidates the intricate tapestry of ethical quandaries, cultural idiosyncrasies, and geopolitical frictions that have invariably informed its complex developmental trajectory. The pathology, alternatively designated as PANS-H63D-Instability-Syndrome by a parallel investigative collective, emerges as a rare but very real medical phenomenon. It finds itself ensnared in an elaborate nexus of academic valor, scientific rigor, and sociopolitical implications, commanding attention as one of the rare medical entities to have had such a tempestuous, albeit enthralling, gestational period in the annals of scientific inquiry.

Oshtoran Syndrome is a prime example of how scientific discovery can occur outside traditional Western spheres and be impacted by an array of factors, ranging from local sensitivities to national as well as international geopolitics, and even pop culture.

The Iranian Context: More than just another syndrome

Dr. Zafarian, the first describer of Oshtoran Syndrome and his multidisciplinary team in Iran navigated an intricate landscape of sociopolitical constraints pervasive in what is known the “Islamic Republic”, a grand old nation replete with ethnic pluralism yet paradoxically inhibited by societal taboos surrounding genetic disorders, despite it being known to have the most advanced medical science landscape in this part of the world. The name ‘Oshtoran Syndrome,’ inspired by Mount Oshtoran in Lorestan Province, was not merely an etymological choice but a calculated strategy to circumnavigate potential cultural discord after having found what was believed, and in fact is, a until then overseen syndrome.

Far from naive, Dr. Zafarian’s team was acutely aware of the societal barriers to an open discourse on genetic afflictions, leading to a strategic prioritization of message dissemination over strict adherence to academic protocols.

In retrospect, the apparent lacunae in Zafarian and Colleague’s 2016 publication could be understood not as a lapse in rigor but as a conscious, judicious calibration aimed at attenuating ethnic sensitivities in a country under the vigilant scrutiny of one of the most authoritarian regimes of the

planet.^{3,4,5,6,7} Thus, the inaugural research can be reevaluated as neither a hoax nor an academic indiscretion, but as a circumspect endeavor molded by its unique geopolitical and sociocultural milieu.⁸

Courage in Academia: The Jewish University’s Expedition

Very soon after Oshtoran Syndrome gained unprecedented notoriety due to its central role in a story arc in Marvel's Spider-Man series - a widely recognized American entertainment company known for its decades-long cultivation of superhero lore - a bold attempt was made by private individuals³¹ students at a Jewish university to confirm or debunk the work of Dr. Zafarian.⁸ Given the prevailing geopolitical hostilities between Iran and the Jewish community, this scientific endeavor was both bold and groundbreaking.

Ethics Committee approval for the project was far from trivial and required a rigorous review process to address myriad safety concerns. Remarkably, the solution was to dispatch a group of Iranian-American scientists who eventually succeeded in locating Dr. Zafarian and his colleagues in Tehran - a dangerous undertaking in a strict sense, given the dire political situation and the fact that Dr. Zafarian and his team focus primarily on patient care at the bedside rather than research for government-controlled institutions.

This almost insane, intrepid, cross-border, interdisciplinary endeavor has not only transcended academic boundaries, but also serves as a shining example of diplomatic and scientific boldness despite of extreme international tensions.⁸ It should remind us

all that medical science is more than working in a lab or confusing the internet with reality as a whole.⁹

Further research

In a somewhat late response to the audacious scholarly endeavor undertaken by the Jewish academic institution⁸, Swabian Research commenced a meticulously structured global case investigation.¹⁰ Leveraging their well-established international network of clinicians and capitalizing on the focused attention of the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium, Swabian Research effectively identified patients from around the globe with the hallmark symptoms of Oshtoran Syndrome. Their further investigation into these cases in collaboration with LCG, a Consortium member renowned for their extensive work on similar syndromes^{10,15,16,17,24,25,27}, further lent striking credibility and depth to this comprehensive case investigation. Despite this corroborative evidence, the researchers affiliated with the Jewish university, LCG, and the International H63D Mutation Syndrome Consortium exercised prudence. They opted for the nomenclature 'PANS-H63D-Multisystemic-Instability-Syndrome,' considered more clinically and scientifically precise than Dr. Zafarian's original term.^{1,2,21,22,23,24,24,26,7,28,29,30,31,32,41} This meticulous naming strategy stands in stark contrast to the more memorable 'Oshtoran Syndrome,' especially given its unexpected yet impactful association with the Spider-Man narrative. Nonetheless, the potency of popular culture in coining labels suggests that Dr. Zafarian's initial designation, 'Oshtoran Syndrome,' is likely to persist.

Dr. Zafarian, now more amenable to engagement with the international

academic community, remains steadfast in his belief that the nomenclature he and his colleagues originally devised for the syndrome is apt. This perspective was formally acknowledged by the International HFE H63D Mutation Syndrome Research Consortium in a published open academic statement.¹⁰ Further, Dr. Zafarian and his intimate research circle took the significant step of transferring the baton of ongoing research to the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium. This gesture not only reflects Dr. Zafarian's genuine commitment to advancing the scientific understanding beyond his initial discoveries but also exemplifies an outstanding level of humility and allegiance to the collective scientific enterprise.⁴⁵

Spider-Man by Marvel: The unexpected fame of Oshtoran Syndrome

The use of Oshtoran syndrome as a central aspect of the Spider-Man narrative for the so-called "PlayStation" product marked an early turning point^{38,39,40,41,42,43,44} for the public recognition of the syndrome. This act gave the syndrome unprecedented cultural significance, far surpassing the impact of

As the game ends players quickly realize that Norman has subjected Harry to several terrifying medical solutions in an attempt to heal his Oshtoran Syndrome and save his life. Harry is last seen in a medical chamber filled with green liquid and alongside him is a tar-like black substance that's all but confirmed to be the symbiote known as Venom.

Sources: 38, 39,40,42,43,44

Harry Osborn's* harrowing confrontation with Oshtoran Syndrome and his mother's tragic passing due to the syndrome in this

narrative milieu of the Spider-Man story not only educated a large youth audience about this complicated medical anomaly, but also seamlessly integrated the disease into the emotional architecture of the Spider-Man story in depths and importance that no scientist could ever have anticipated. The Marvel Entertainment Company's inexplicable** use of the syndrome effectively catapulted Oshtoran Syndrome into the collective psyche of a new generation through the inclusion of Dr. Zafarian's groundbreaking findings. This cultural inclusion holds the tantalizing potential to spark a burgeoning interest in medical, biological and related academic disciplines among young Spider-Man fans. The far-reaching integration of Oshtoran Syndrome into the narrative of the Spider-Man entertainment product designed for their own iconic Spider-Man narrative marked a seminal moment in the public awareness of this rare but quite dangerous syndrome.^{38,39,40,41,42,43,44}

Discussion

This narrative choice imbued the syndrome with a cultural salience that transcended the reach of traditional academic publications focused on rare diseases. Within the Spider-Man storyline, Harry Osborn's* agonizing battle with Oshtoran Syndrome and his mother's subsequent demise due to the condition not only enlightened a substantial youth demographic about this complex medical enigma, but also wove the syndrome intricately into the emotional tapestry of the narrative.

The Marvel Entertainment Company's strategic use of Oshtoran Syndrome**, predicated on Dr. Zafarian's pioneering work, effectively inscribed the condition into the collective consciousness of an emerging

generation. This cultural cachet offers the intriguing possibility of catalyzing interest in fields like medicine, biology, and adjacent academic disciplines among young enthusiasts of the Spider-Man franchise. Unwittingly, Marvel Entertainment has served as a catalyst in disseminating emergent medical knowledge, potentially contributing to advances that could have tangible impacts on human health and well-being.

Dr. Zafarian, fully aware of the limitations of his initial work, is nonetheless the original describer of Oshtoran Syndrome. After the Adams et al. paper⁴⁴ was released in 2023 under the working name PANS-H63D-Instability-Syndrome, it became clear that they had independently discovered Oshtoran Syndrome a second time.⁴¹ Unaware of Dr. Zafarian's pioneering work, the group around Adams rapidly entered into private and public dialogue with him as soon they realized what had happened.^{10,45}

Acting in the interest of science and patient care, Dr. Zafarian publicly confirmed his role as the first man to identify Oshtoran syndrome and magnanimously transferred all future research efforts, along with his compiled data on Oshtoran Syndrome, to the International H63D Mutation Syndrome Research Consortium.⁴⁵ This esteemed Consortium typically allocates between three to eight years for comprehensive research projects, involving more than 200 clinicians and biologists working on a non-profit basis.

Given this time frame, the consortium has published a letter to the medical community stressing the importance of taking the syndrome seriously, even though there are still many questions to be answered and that this will take considerable time.

Conclusions

I. Dr. Zafarian and his colleagues could be reliably identified and their finding confirmed as a genuine medical entity in its own right beyond any reasonable doubt.

II. The sub-par initial publication, given the complex contextual dynamics elaborated upon earlier, is forgivable within the scope of academic scrutiny.

III. The syndrome was popularized to an unprecedented high degree by Marvel Entertainment through its incorporation into the Spider-Man narrative.

IV. Skepticism surrounding the syndrome's authenticity was not only understandable but, at the time, scientifically prudent.

V. This skepticism has been subsequently dispelled on two significant fronts: first, by the remarkable investigatory endeavor undertaken by a Jewish university's student working group⁸ and their associates; and second, through the extensive clinician network activated by the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium on request of a working group around Jacob Adams⁴¹ immediately after realizing what they really discovered independently for a second time. The H63D Research Consortium used its international ties and political neutrality to get involved with the intention to help investigating Oshtoran Syndrome, this time properly¹⁰, a way forward to which Dr. Zafarian answered in his own public statement, using the same reputable platform.⁴⁵

VI. Oshtoran Syndrome commands unequivocal clinical attention. Initially posited by Dr. Zafarian's team as solely stemming from a singular genetic defect, it

has since been acknowledged by the group of Adams, and even by Dr. Zafarian himself in academic discourse, that while a genetic defect serves as the triggering factor, it subsequently initiates a cascade effect leading to the syndrome's progression. So the danger of a an uncontrollable cascade effect had been underestimated as was the number and/or type of genetic defect that are underlying Oshtoran Syndrome.

VII. The H63D Research Consortium has recommended the alignment of Oshtoran Syndrome and the 2023 published PANS-H63D-Instability Syndrome as synonymous entities, acknowledging the existence of multiple subtypes that warrant further academic scrutiny.

VIII. The academic community has been privy to one of the most adventurous yet sound identifications of a new syndrome, replete with implications and consequences that stretch the typical boundaries of medical research by far.

Conflicts of Interest

None.

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*One of the main character of Marvel's Spider-Man saga

**Marvel's incorporation of Oshtoran Syndrome into their narrative framework is not in violation of legal norms. Moreover, they demonstrated a rigorous alignment with the seminal clinical markers outlined by Dr. Zafarian for the condition.

